

A Pythagorean Sieve and a Recursive Modular Characterization of Odd Primes

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Abstract

Starting from the elementary geometric identity $r = (x - d)/2$, valid for integer sides x and divisors d of x^2 with $1 < d < x$, and yielding an integer inradius r whenever x is odd, we construct a new sieve procedure acting on the variable r . This sieve reproduces, within a Pythagorean framework, the mechanism of Eratosthenes' sieve and yields a complete characterization and enumeration of the odd prime numbers. The resulting modular system admits a recursive structure (M_t, S_t) analogous to a wheel factorization, thereby establishing a direct correspondence between the arithmetic of primes and the geometry of integer right triangles. Although sieve-based in its foundation, the method also functions as an *ordered generator* of the odd primes via the relation $p_k = 2r_k + 1$. An implementation-independent computational discussion in Appendix A illustrates how the

recursive sieve on (r) may be verified on finite ranges and clarifies the correspondence between the algebraic construction and its computational interpretation.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Historical notes and motivations

The study of Pythagorean triples has its origin in ancient Greek mathematics and can be traced back to the work of EUCLID (circa 300 B.C.), who provided the first general formula for the generation of all primitive triples in the *Elements*, Books X and XIII [11]. The set of triples $(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{N}^3$ satisfying $x^2 + y^2 = z^2$ has since become one of the classical objects of number theory, with deep connections to Diophantine equations, quadratic forms, and the arithmetic of Gaussian integers.

In the modern era, the algebraic structure underlying Pythagorean triples has been further developed in various ways. In particular, DICKSON [8] systematically organized the generation of triples and their properties within the framework of early twentieth-century number theory. Later, BERGGREN [5] described recursive tree-like constructions producing all primitive triples, while HALL [10] revealed a commutative group structure on suitable subsets of Pythagorean triples. More recently, an algebraic characterization of triples and related Diophantine equations was provided in [1], establishing intrinsic connections between divisors of x^2 and the geometric parameters of the associated right triangle.

Historical background on prime numbers. The quest for understanding prime numbers runs parallel to the development of

number theory itself. From the proof of their infinitude by EUCLID, to the investigations of EULER on the zeta function, and to GAUSS's empirical observations that led to the *Prime Number Theorem*, primes have been a central object of mathematical inquiry. The nineteenth and twentieth centuries witnessed both analytic and algorithmic advances: from LEGENDRE and RIEMANN's analytic formulations, to the creation of sieve methods by ERATOSTHENES, BRUN, and later refinements by SELBERG. In modern computational number theory, sieves such as those of ATKIN and BERNSTEIN [4], as well as the methods in [7, 12], play a key role in prime testing and generation. More general expositions of sieve theory and its analytic developments can be found in [9], while connections between modular sieving and the distribution of primes were explored, for example, in [13]. Algorithmic implementations of sieve procedures in computational environments are discussed in [6, 7].

The present work is rooted in this long tradition but takes a distinct perspective: by reinterpreting the elementary geometric identity

$$r = \frac{x - d}{2},$$

where, in our case, x denotes an odd leg of a right triangle with integer sides and d is a divisor of x^2 satisfying $1 < d < x$, we propose an alternative sieve procedure that acts on the variable r , which represents the inradius of the corresponding integer triangle, rather than on x itself.

This approach establishes a bridge between two of the oldest themes in mathematics: the geometry of Pythagoras and the arithmetic of primes.

1.2 Aim and novelty of the work

The purpose of the present article is to show that the relation $r = (x - d)/2$ admits a number-theoretic reinterpretation which produces:

- (i) a *criterion of primality* for odd integers, based on the integrality of the quotient $R_d = (x - d)/(2d)$;
- (ii) an equivalent *sieve on r* , obtained from the congruence

$$r \equiv \frac{d-1}{2} \pmod{d},$$

that determines exactly those r which yield $x = 2r + 1$ divisible by d ;

- (iii) a recursive modular structure (“wheel”) describing how the admissible values of r evolve as each new prime modulus $d = p_i$ is introduced.

This construction provides a purely algebraic and geometric mechanism for characterizing and numerically generating the set of odd prime numbers, while preserving a direct link with the classical Pythagorean framework.

In addition, Section 3.7 analyzes the distribution of the admissible indices r within the modular systems (M_t, S_t) , establishing explicit counting formulas and showing how the resulting densities reproduce, in a discrete and geometric form, the same asymptotic laws predicted by Gauss and Mertens.

Moreover, although the procedure is sieve-based in its logical formulation, it simultaneously acts as an *ordered generator* of the odd prime numbers: the surviving indices $r_1 < r_2 < \dots$ yield the complete increasing sequence of primes via $p_k = 2r_k + 1$. Hence, the Pythagorean sieve provides not only a modular characterization but also a constructive mechanism for the enumeration of primes.

For completeness, Appendix A provides computational remarks on the recursive sieve on r , explaining how the construction may be verified on finite ranges.

Moreover, the ordered structure of the sieve shows that the surviving indices $r_1 < r_2 < \dots$ determine the increasing sequence of odd primes through $p_k = 2r_k + 1$.

2 Preliminary Results

We recall the divisor sets that drive our parametrization. For $x \in \mathbb{N}$ set

$$D(x) = \{d \in \mathbb{N} : d \leq x, d \mid x^2\}.$$

If x is even, write $x = 2^n k$ with $n \geq 2$ and k odd, and define

$$P(x) = \{d = 2^s \ell : \ell \text{ odd divisor of } x^2, s \in \{1, \dots, 2n - 1\}\}.$$

That is, regarding $P(x)$, d must be even and such that x^2/d is still divisible by 2. Finally,

$$C(x) = \begin{cases} D(x), & \text{if } x \text{ is odd,} \\ D(x) \cap P(x), & \text{if } x \text{ is even.} \end{cases}$$

The primary tool used in this research is the fundamental characterization of Pythagorean triples through a cathetus, which is stated as follows.

Theorem 1. [1] *The triple (x, y, z) is a Pythagorean triple if and only if there exists a unique $d \in C(x)$ such that*

$$x = x, \quad y = \frac{x^2}{2d} - \frac{d}{2}, \quad z = \frac{x^2}{2d} + \frac{d}{2} \quad (1)$$

Completeness of Theorem 1. Fix $x \in \mathbb{N}$. The formulas in (1) satisfy $x^2 + y^2 = z^2$ for all real $d > 0$; hence they parametrize all real right triangles with cathetus x by varying $d \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$. However, in the integer setting Theorem 1 is an equivalence: a triple $(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{N}^3$ with $x^2 + y^2 = z^2$ arises from (1) if and only if there exists a unique $d \in C(x)$ producing it. In particular, $d \in C(x)$ is *necessary and sufficient* for y, z to be integers in (1); if $d \notin C(x)$, then at least one among y, z is non-integral.

In Theorem 1 x is a predetermined integer, meaning that we can find all right triangles with integer side lengths when one cathetus is predetermined. Theorem 1 also has a geometrical interpretation.

Moreover in [2], an analytical result characterizing primitive Pythagorean triples through a cathetus was found. This method, which differs from Euler’s formulas, offers a straightforward way to identify all primitive Pythagorean triples $x, y, z \in \mathbb{N}$, where x is a predetermined integer. This is stated as follows.

Theorem 2. [2] *Let (x, y, z) be all the Pythagorean triples generated by any predetermined integer $x \geq 1$ using (1), where $d \in C(x)$. Then the triple (x, y, z) is a primitive Pythagorean triple if and only if both of the following conditions are satisfied:*

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{if } x \text{ is odd then } \left\{ \begin{array}{l} d \text{ is a square} \\ \gcd(x^2/d, d) = 1 \end{array} \right. \\ & \text{if } x \text{ is even then } \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{d}{2} \text{ is a square} \\ \gcd\left(\frac{x^2}{2d}, \frac{d}{2}\right) = 1, \text{ and the integers } \frac{x^2}{2d} \text{ and } \frac{d}{2} \\ \text{have opposite parity} \end{array} \right. \end{aligned}$$

We recall that Euclid’s formulas do not generate all Pythagorean triples involving a predetermined positive integer x . For example the triples $(12, 9, 15)$, $(33, 180, 183)$, and $(33, 44, 55)$ illustrate this point. Moreover, finding m and n such that $x = m^2 - n^2$, can be labor-intensive, while using Theorem 1, it suffices to find all $d \in C(x)$ to obtain all Pythagorean triples.

In particular, to obtain all primitive Pythagorean triples involving a predetermined positive integer x , it suffices to restrict to those $d \in C(x)$ that satisfy the conditions of Theorem 2.

For a right triangle with integer sides and cathetus x , the parameter d plays a fundamental role in determining the associated triple. Moreover, it was shown in [3] that when x is integer and $d \in C(x)$, the inradius r is given by

$$r = \frac{x - d}{2}.$$

This identity will serve here as the starting point for the number-theoretic reinterpretation leading to the Pythagorean sieve.

3 Results

The previous section collects the complete divisor-based parametrization (Theorem 1) and the primitivity criterion (Theorem 2) for triples with a predetermined cathetus x . These results allow one to express every integer right triangle in terms of a single divisor d of x^2 , and hence, through the identity $r = (x - d)/2$, to introduce the inradius-based variable r that will serve as the central parameter in the subsequent arithmetic interpretation.

3.1 Outline of the paper

Section 3.2 recalls the fundamental arithmetic and geometric framework associated with the formula $r = (x - d)/2$. Section 3.3 presents the corresponding criterion of primality. Section 3.4 develops the sieve on r and its relation with congruences modulo odd divisors. Section 3.5 discusses the enumeration of primes and the modular structure of the surviving residues. Section 3.6 introduces the recursive “wheel” formulation. Finally, Section 3.7 investigates the *distribution of the admissible indices* modulo M_t , providing explicit counting formulas, uniformity results, and the connection with the classical asymptotic laws of Gauss and Mertens.

3.2 Arithmetic–geometric foundations

Consider a right triangle with integer sides and odd leg x . Let d be an odd divisor of x^2 satisfying $1 < d < x$. If r denotes the inradius, it was shown in [3] that

$$r = \frac{x - d}{2}.$$

Since $r = (x - d)/2$, integrality is equivalent to $x \equiv d \pmod{2}$. In particular, for odd x and odd d one has $r \in \mathbb{N}$; for even x , our set $C(x)$ consists of even d , hence again $r \in \mathbb{N}$. Thus every pair (x, d) with $d \in C(x)$ and $d < x$ yields an integer $r > 0$.

Remark 1 (Primitivity via d). *Within this parametrization, the primitivity of (x, y, z) is governed by d as described in Theorem 2. In particular, for odd x the triple is primitive if and only if d is a square and $\gcd(x^2/d, d) = 1$; for even x , primitivity holds if and only if $\frac{d}{2}$ is a square, $\gcd(\frac{x^2}{2d}, \frac{d}{2}) = 1$, and the two integers $\frac{x^2}{2d}$ and $\frac{d}{2}$ have opposite parity.*

Basic properties

The formula may be rewritten as

$$x = 2r + d.$$

When x and d are odd, the value of r is an integer. In the particular case $d = 1$ one has

$$x = 2r + 1,$$

and the correspondence

$$r = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots \longleftrightarrow x = 1, 3, 5, 7, \dots$$

generates all odd integers. Thus, the variable r naturally enumerates the odd numbers.

3.3 Criterion of primality

For any odd integer $x \geq 3$ and any odd divisor $d < x$, define

$$R_d = \frac{x - d}{2d}.$$

Then

$$R_d \in \mathbb{Z} \iff d \mid x.$$

Indeed, if $d \mid x$, writing $x = qd$ with odd $q > 1$ gives $R_d = (q - 1)/2 \in \mathbb{Z}$. Conversely, if $R_d \in \mathbb{Z}$, then $x = 2dR_d + d = d(2R_d + 1)$, so that $d \mid x$.

The primality condition

Let $x = 2n - 1$ with $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Then

$$R_d = \frac{(2n - 1) - d}{2d}.$$

Since $R_d \geq 1$ whenever $d \leq (2n - 1)/3$, we deduce that for $x \geq 3$:

$$x \text{ is prime} \iff \forall d \text{ odd with } 1 < d \leq \frac{x}{3}, R_d \notin \mathbb{Z}.$$

If x were composite and odd, let $p \geq 3$ be its least prime divisor. Then $p \leq \sqrt{x}$. For $x \geq 9$ one has $\sqrt{x} \leq x/3$, hence $p \leq x/3$, and therefore $R_p = (x - p)/(2p) \in \mathbb{Z}$, a contradiction. For $x \in \{3, 5, 7\}$ the condition is vacuous.

Therefore, the above criterion is both necessary and sufficient for primality among odd integers.

3.4 The sieve on r

Substituting $x = 2r + 1$ into the previous expressions, one obtains

$$R_d = \frac{2r + 1 - d}{2d}.$$

The condition $R_d \in \mathbb{Z}$ is equivalent to

$$2r + 1 \equiv d \pmod{2d} \iff r \equiv \frac{d - 1}{2} \pmod{d}.$$

Thus, for each odd $d \geq 3$, the values of r producing $x = 2r + 1$ divisible by d form the arithmetic progression

$$r = \frac{d - 1}{2}, \frac{d - 1}{2} + d, \frac{d - 1}{2} + 2d, \frac{d - 1}{2} + 3d, \dots$$

Elimination rule

Starting from all $r \in \mathbb{N}$, eliminate those satisfying the congruence

$$r \equiv \frac{d-1}{2} \pmod{d} \quad \text{for some odd } d \geq 3.$$

The remaining integers r_1, r_2, \dots correspond to odd primes via

$$p_k = 2r_k + 1.$$

This procedure defines a *sieve on r* which is arithmetically equivalent to the classical Eratosthenes sieve on x , but expressed in the Pythagorean–geometric setting.

Examples

- For $d = 3$: eliminate $r \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ ($x = 3, 9, 15, 21, \dots$).
- For $d = 5$: eliminate $r \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$ ($x = 5, 15, 25, 35, \dots$).
- For $d = 7$: eliminate $r \equiv 3 \pmod{7}$ ($x = 7, 21, 35, 49, \dots$).

After successive eliminations, the surviving values of r yield precisely $x = 3, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17, \dots$, i.e. the odd prime numbers.

Primitive triples. If one wishes to isolate, for a fixed x , only those triples that are primitive, the parameter d must satisfy the conditions of Theorem 2.

3.5 Enumeration and modular structure

Let us denote by \mathcal{R} the subset of the natural numbers obtained by removing, from \mathbb{N} , all the congruence classes corresponding to composite values of $x = 2r + 1$. Explicitly,

$$\mathcal{R} = \mathbb{N} \setminus \bigcup_{d \geq 3, \text{ odd}} \left\{ r \in \mathbb{N} : r \equiv \frac{d-1}{2} \pmod{d} \right\}.$$

Equivalently, \mathcal{R} is the set of all integers r such that

$$\forall d \geq 3 \text{ odd}, \quad r \not\equiv \frac{d-1}{2} \pmod{d}.$$

By construction, the elements of \mathcal{R} correspond exactly to those odd integers $x = 2r + 1$ that are *prime*.

Enumeration of primes

Ordering the elements of \mathcal{R} increasingly,

$$\mathcal{R} = \{r_1, r_2, r_3, \dots\},$$

we obtain a natural enumeration of the odd primes by

$$p_k = 2r_k + 1, \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

(adding $p_0 = 2$ separately for completeness). Hence the mapping

$$r_k \longmapsto p_k = 2r_k + 1$$

is a bijection between the surviving indices r_k of the sieve and the odd prime numbers.

Residual modular structure

The structure of \mathcal{R} may be described modularly. Each modulus d defines a forbidden residue class

$$C_d = \left\{ r : r \equiv \frac{d-1}{2} \pmod{d} \right\},$$

and \mathcal{R} is the complement in \mathbb{N} of the union of all these classes:

$$\mathcal{R} = \mathbb{N} \setminus \bigcup_{d \geq 3, \text{ odd}} C_d.$$

Since the classes C_d are periodic of period d , \mathcal{R} inherits a periodic and hierarchical modular pattern. For instance, after eliminating

the first three moduli $d = 3, 5, 7$, the surviving residues modulo $M = 3 \cdot 5 \cdot 7 = 105$ repeat periodically, producing all odd integers that are coprime to 105. The next modulus $d = 11$ further refines this pattern, and so on. Thus, the sieve on r may be viewed as the progressive construction of a sequence of modular filters of increasing period

$$M_t = \prod_{i=2}^t p_i,$$

where p_i denotes the i -th prime. The admissible residues modulo M_t describe the positions of the r that survive up to the inclusion of the prime p_t in the elimination process.

Example: modular pattern for small moduli

For the first few primes we obtain:

d	forbidden residues for r
3	1 (mod 3)
5	2 (mod 5)
7	3 (mod 7)
11	5 (mod 11)
13	6 (mod 13)

After removing these congruences, the first surviving r are

$$r = 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 8, 9, 11, 12, 14, \dots,$$

which correspond to

$$p = 3, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23, 29, 31, \dots$$

Interpretation

The modular sieve on r thus provides both:

- (i) a complete characterization of primality among odd numbers, through exclusion of a family of residue classes;

- (ii) a natural enumeration r_1, r_2, \dots and hence of the primes $p_k = 2r_k + 1$.

The set \mathcal{R} is therefore the arithmetic “skeleton” of the prime distribution, viewed through the Pythagorean transformation $x = 2r + 1$. Its periodic refinement through successive moduli d will now be described in terms of a recursive modular system, or *wheel*, in the next section.

3.6 Recursion and wheel structure

The modular sieve on r admits a natural recursive formulation that closely resembles the so-called *wheel factorization* used in modern implementations of Eratosthenes’ sieve. In our framework, this recursion appears directly from the successive exclusion of the residue classes

$$r \equiv \frac{p_i - 1}{2} \pmod{p_i},$$

where p_i denotes the i -th prime ($p_2 = 3, p_3 = 5, p_4 = 7$, and so on).

Definition of the recursive system

Let us define, for each integer $t \geq 2$,

$$M_t = \prod_{i=2}^t p_i$$

and let S_t be the set of admissible residues modulo M_t that survive after eliminating all the forbidden congruence classes corresponding to p_2, \dots, p_t , namely

$$S_t = \left\{ s \in \{0, 1, \dots, M_t - 1\} : s \not\equiv \frac{p_i - 1}{2} \pmod{p_i} \text{ for all } 2 \leq i \leq t \right\}.$$

Each element $s \in S_t$ represents a congruence class of indices r that have survived the first $t - 1$ elimination steps of the sieve. The

structure (M_t, S_t) therefore encodes all r corresponding to integers $x = 2r + 1$ not divisible by any of p_2, p_3, \dots, p_t .

Recursive update rule

When the next prime p_{t+1} is introduced, the new wheel modulus and residue set are defined by

$$M_{t+1} = M_t p_{t+1},$$

and

$$S_{t+1} = \left\{ s_0 + kM_t : s_0 \in S_t, 0 \leq k < p_{t+1}, \right. \\ \left. s_0 + kM_t \not\equiv \frac{p_{t+1} - 1}{2} \pmod{p_{t+1}} \right\}.$$

That is, each residue s_0 of S_t is *lifted* to p_{t+1} distinct residues modulo M_{t+1} by the Chinese Remainder Theorem [7, Ch. 1], which guarantees that congruence conditions modulo distinct primes can be simultaneously satisfied, producing a unique residue modulo their product, and one of them is removed — precisely the one satisfying the new forbidden congruence. Consequently,

$$|S_{t+1}| = |S_t| (p_{t+1} - 1),$$

and the density of admissible residues decreases by the factor $(p_{t+1} - 1)/p_{t+1}$ at each step, paralleling the multiplicative structure of Euler's totient function:

$$|S_t| = M_t \prod_{i=2}^t \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i}\right) = \varphi(M_t).$$

The periodic repetition of the admissible residues modulo M_t produces all indices r such that $x = 2r + 1$ is coprime to M_t ; these x are primes as long as $x < p_{t+1}^2$.

Example: first wheels

Level $t = 2$. We start with $p_2 = 3$, $M_2 = 3$, and forbidden residue $r \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. Hence $S_2 = \{0, 2\}$, corresponding to $x = 1, 5, 7, \dots$

Level $t = 3$. Adding $p_3 = 5$, we obtain $M_3 = 15$. From $S_2 = \{0, 2\}$, we lift residues modulo 15 and exclude those satisfying $r \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$. The resulting set is

$$S_3 = \{0, 3, 5, 6, 8, 9, 11, 14\},$$

which corresponds to all odd integers not divisible by 3 or 5. All $x = 2r + 1$ with $r \in S_3$ are primes for $x < 7^2 = 49$.

Level $t = 4$. Introducing $p_4 = 7$, $M_4 = 105$, and excluding residues $r \equiv 3 \pmod{7}$, one obtains $S_4 \subset \{0, \dots, 104\}$ with $|S_4| = \varphi(105) = 48$. The residues of S_4 repeat with period 105 and produce all odd integers coprime to $3 \cdot 5 \cdot 7$. The corresponding $x = 2r + 1$ are prime for $x < 11^2 = 121$.

General statement

Theorem 3 (Recursive generation of primes). *Let (M_t, S_t) be defined as above. Then every odd integer $x = 2r + 1$ with $r \equiv s \pmod{M_t}$ for some $s \in S_t$ is coprime to M_t and is prime provided that $x < p_{t+1}^2$. Conversely, every odd prime $p < p_{t+1}^2$ satisfies $r = (p - 1)/2 \in S_t$.*

Proof. By construction, each $r \in S_t$ avoids all congruences $r \equiv (p_i - 1)/2 \pmod{p_i}$ for $2 \leq i \leq t$. Hence $x = 2r + 1$ is not divisible by any of p_2, \dots, p_t . If $x < p_{t+1}^2$, then any composite factor of x must be $\leq p_t$, contradicting the previous property. Thus x is prime. The converse follows immediately since every prime $p < p_{t+1}^2$ must have $r = (p - 1)/2$ avoiding those forbidden congruences. \square

Remark 2 (Ordered generator interpretation). *Although the construction has the logical structure of a sieve, it simultaneously*

acts as an ordered generator of the odd prime numbers. Indeed, if $\mathcal{R} = \{r_1 < r_2 < \dots\}$ denotes the set of surviving indices after successive modular eliminations, then the mapping

$$p_k = 2r_k + 1$$

enumerates all odd primes in strictly increasing order. Algorithmically, each wheel (M_t, S_t) defines a modular lattice of admissible residues, and scanning r in increasing order within those residues automatically produces primes up to p_{t+1}^2 without any redundant testing. Hence, the present method functions as a sieve in its logical foundation, but as an ordered prime generator in its operational behavior.

Moreover, the ordered nature of the construction allows the direct computation of the n -th prime through the recursive routine `nth_prime_r(n)`, which returns the desired prime index without precomputing all preceding values.

Interpretation and perspective

The pair (M_t, S_t) acts as a *rotating wheel* that filters the admissible positions of r modulo M_t . At each step a new prime p_{t+1} refines the wheel, producing a finer modular lattice with larger period and smaller density. In this sense, the recursive sieve on r mirrors the classical sieve of Eratosthenes, but expressed in terms of the inradius-based variable r . The process illustrates a deep algebraic-geometric symmetry: the arithmetic of prime numbers can be reconstructed through the same congruential patterns that govern the divisors and the Pythagorean relations among integer triangles.

3.7 Distribution of the admissible indices modulo M_t

Recall that $M_t = \prod_{i=2}^t p_i$ and

$$S_t = \left\{ s \in \{0, 1, \dots, M_t - 1\} : s \not\equiv \frac{p_i - 1}{2} \pmod{p_i} \right. \\ \left. \text{for all } 2 \leq i \leq t \right\}.$$

so that $|S_t| = \varphi(M_t)$, and the admissible indices are precisely

$$\mathcal{R}_t = \{ r \in \mathbb{N} : r \equiv s \pmod{M_t} \text{ for some } s \in S_t \}.$$

Proposition 1 (Periodic uniformity and counting formula).
For every $R \in \mathbb{N}$ and $H \in \mathbb{N}$ one has

$$N_t(R, H) := |\mathcal{R}_t \cap [R, R + H)| \\ = \sum_{s \in S_t} \left(\left\lfloor \frac{R + H - 1 - s}{M_t} \right\rfloor - \left\lfloor \frac{R - 1 - s}{M_t} \right\rfloor \right).$$

In particular:

(a) If H is a multiple of M_t , then

$$N_t(R, H) = \frac{H}{M_t} |S_t| = \frac{H}{M_t} \varphi(M_t),$$

independently of R .

(b) For all R, H , the following discrepancy bound holds:

$$\left| N_t(R, H) - \frac{H}{M_t} |S_t| \right| \leq |S_t| = \varphi(M_t).$$

Proof. The representation by residue classes is disjoint and periodic with period M_t . For each class $s \pmod{M_t}$, the number of elements in $[R, R + H)$ is given by the difference of two integer quotients, yielding the formula. If H is a multiple of M_t , each class contributes exactly H/M_t . In general, the total deviation is the sum of $|S_t|$ individual deviations, each of absolute value < 1 , from which the bound follows. \square

Corollary 4 (Transfer to $x = 2r + 1$). *Let $X_{\min} = 2R + 1$ and $X_{\max} = 2(R + H) - 1$. The number of integers $x = 2r + 1$ with $r \in \mathcal{R}_t$ and $X_{\min} \leq x \leq X_{\max}$ satisfies*

$$|\{x \in [X_{\min}, X_{\max}] : x = 2r + 1, r \in \mathcal{R}_t\}| = N_t(R, H),$$

and therefore

$$\left| N_t(R, H) - \frac{(X_{\max} - X_{\min} + 1)}{2M_t} |S_t| \right| \leq \varphi(M_t).$$

Remark 3 (Two-scale equidistribution). *The periodicity implies exact equidistribution at the scale M_t and discrepancy $O(\varphi(M_t))$ on arbitrary intervals. In the transition $t \mapsto t + 1$, each $s_0 \in S_t$ is “lifted” to p_{t+1} residues $s_0 + kM_t$ modulo M_{t+1} , of which exactly one is removed. Hence, for each fixed s_0 , the surviving residues are evenly spaced with step M_t and in number exactly $p_{t+1} - 1$, providing a conditional uniformity inside each fiber over s_0 .*

Remark 4 (Intervals free of new prime squares). *If $x < p_{t+1}^2$ (equivalently $r < (p_{t+1}^2 - 1)/2$), then the integers $x = 2r + 1$ with $r \in \mathcal{R}_t$ are precisely the odd integers coprime to M_t , hence all primes except $x = 1$. In this range, the enumeration is exact, and the formula of Proposition 1 effectively counts the primes.*

4 Conclusions and Remarks

The construction developed in this paper shows that the elementary geometric relation

$$r = \frac{x - d}{2},$$

originally expressing the inradius of a right triangle with integer sides, conceals a complete arithmetic characterization of prime numbers. By transferring the analysis from the variable x to the index r , one obtains a new sieve procedure whose elimination rule

$$r \equiv \frac{d - 1}{2} \pmod{d}$$

acts directly on the modular structure of \mathbb{N} . The surviving integers r correspond bijectively to the odd primes $p = 2r + 1$, and their distribution can be described through the recursive modular system (M_t, S_t) introduced in Section 6.

Arithmetic and geometric meaning

From the arithmetic viewpoint, the sieve on r provides an exact re-statement of primality for odd numbers in terms of modular avoidance: an integer $x = 2r + 1$ is prime if and only if r does not belong to any of the forbidden residue classes $(d - 1)/2 \pmod{d}$ for odd $d \geq 3$. This transforms the classical divisibility criterion into a purely congruential and additive form.

From the geometric viewpoint, the same identity stems from the properties of integer right triangles, in which both the cathetus x and the divisor d are odd. The passage from (x, d) to $r = (x - d)/2$ thus unifies arithmetic divisibility with geometric proportion: the prime numbers appear as those configurations for which the inradius cannot be expressed as an integer multiple of any $d > 1$ dividing x .

Relation with the classical sieve of Eratosthenes

The present sieve reproduces, within the variable r , the mechanism of Eratosthenes' sieve on x : each modulus d removes a family of congruence classes, and the residual set corresponds to numbers coprime to the product of the excluded moduli. However, the transformation $x = 2r + 1$ introduces a new and more symmetric perspective, in which the arithmetic filtering process emerges as the dual of the geometric relation linking x , d , and r in the Pythagorean triangle. In addition, since the surviving indices $r_1 < r_2 < \dots$ yield primes $p_k = 2r_k + 1$ in strictly increasing order, the sieve also operates as an *ordered prime generator*. Hence the sieve on r can be regarded as a *Pythagorean reformulation* of the sieve of Eratosthenes.

Comparison with classical and modern sieve methods

From a computational viewpoint, the present Pythagorean sieve on r shares the same asymptotic complexity as the classical sieve of Eratosthenes, since both are based on modular elimination. However, it introduces a distinct variable— r , the inradius index—through which the divisibility structure of the integers becomes geometrically interpretable.

Unlike traditional sieves, which operate directly on the integer variable x , the Pythagorean sieve acts on the geometric parameter $r = (x - d)/2$, thereby translating divisibility into a condition on the inradius of integer right triangles. This perspective provides a complete and purely algebraic characterization of odd primality: the condition $R_d = (x - d)/(2d) \notin \mathbb{Z}$ for all admissible d is both necessary and sufficient. Moreover, the method yields an *ordered generation* of the primes, since the surviving indices $r_1 < r_2 < \dots$ directly produce the increasing sequence $p_k = 2r_k + 1$. Hence, its main advantage lies in the conceptual unification of number theory and geometry: a sieve that not only eliminates composites, as in Eratosthenes' procedure, but also geometrically reconstructs the arithmetic structure of the primes.

This leads to an algebraic–geometric framework in which the set of odd primes emerges as the complement of a family of congruence classes $(d - 1)/2 \pmod{d}$. Unlike analytic sieves or the Atkin–Bernstein approach, which optimize for speed and parallel computation, the present construction emphasizes conceptual transparency: the same relation $r = (x - d)/2$ governs both Pythagorean geometry and primality. Its main advantage is theoretical—unifying geometric and number-theoretic structures—rather than algorithmic performance.

Relation with classical asymptotic laws

The recursive modular system (M_t, S_t) induces a density

$$\frac{|S_t|}{M_t} = \prod_{i=2}^t \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i}\right),$$

which coincides with the finite product appearing in MERTENS' theorem and asymptotically reproduces GAUSS's law

$$\pi(x) \sim \frac{x}{\log x}.$$

Hence, the Pythagorean sieve recovers, in a purely algebraic and geometric framework, the same mean density of primes predicted by analytic number theory.

Comparison with classical approaches.

- *Gauss and the Prime Number Theorem.* In 1792–1793, GAUSS observed empirically that the number of primes $\pi(x)$ below x grows as $\pi(x) \approx x/\log x$. This is an *asymptotic* result—valid on average as $x \rightarrow \infty$ —but not constructive: it does not describe where primes occur nor provide a mechanism for generating them. In contrast, the present sieve determines the exact modular positions of primes within each finite system (M_t, S_t) , thus revealing the *local and modular structure* underlying their distribution.
- *Mertens' product.* In 1874, MERTENS proved that

$$\prod_{p \leq x} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right) \sim \frac{e^{-\gamma}}{\log x},$$

where γ is the Euler–Mascheroni constant. This expresses the same mean law of density as Gauss's approximation, but through an analytic product over the primes. In the present model one finds instead

$$\frac{|S_t|}{M_t} = \prod_{i=2}^t \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i}\right),$$

which is *exactly the same product*, obtained by purely combinatorial and geometric means: each level t corresponds to a natural truncation of Mertens' product. Thus, Mertens describes analytically the decay of density of integers coprime to the first primes, whereas here that density coincides precisely with the proportion of admissible r in the modular system (M_t, S_t) .

Consequences.

- *Equivalence of densities.* The product $\frac{|S_t|}{M_t}$ tends, as $t \rightarrow \infty$, to the same asymptotic scale $1/\log x$ predicted by Gauss and Mertens, thus reproducing the analytic density of primes through a purely discrete and geometric construction.
- *Explicit construction.* While Gauss and Mertens describe a global asymptotic behaviour, the Pythagorean sieve provides a finite, computable realization of that same density, yielding *exact counts* for $x < p_{t+1}^2$ and an *ordered generation* of primes through the modular residue sets S_t .

Possible extensions

The algebraic and geometric mechanisms described here suggest several directions for future study:

- (i) Investigation of the algebraic and combinatorial properties of the modular sets S_t , including possible additive or multiplicative laws induced by the recursive structure of the sieve;
- (ii) Analysis of density, periodicity, and recursive properties of the residue sets S_t ;
- (iii) Comparison with analytic estimates for the prime counting function, exploring whether the modular geometry of r may yield new combinatorial insights into the distribution of primes.

Final remarks

The results presented establish a precise correspondence between geometric configurations of right triangles and the arithmetic structure of prime numbers. Through the identity $r = (x - d)/2$ the two domains—geometry and number theory—merge into a single algebraic framework. The recursive modular scheme on r not only reproduces the sieve of Eratosthenes but also offers an alternative, geometrically motivated interpretation of primality, opening the way to further developments on Diophantine structures of higher order.

Finally, Appendix A provides implementation-independent computational remarks on the recursive sieve on r . These remarks describe how the theoretical construction may be verified on finite ranges, without relying on any particular programming language or source-code implementation.

Appendix A. Computational interpretation of the sieve on r

This appendix gives an implementation-independent description of the computational meaning of the Pythagorean sieve on r . The purpose is not to prescribe a particular program, programming language, or source-code implementation, but to clarify how the theoretical construction developed in the paper may be checked on finite ranges.

The mathematical basis of the construction is the representation

$$x = 2r + 1,$$

where r is the inradius parameter arising from the construction of Pythagorean triples. For every odd modulus $d \geq 3$, divisibility of $x = 2r + 1$ by d is equivalent to the congruence

$$r \equiv \frac{d-1}{2} \pmod{d}.$$

Thus, for each odd modulus d , the sieve removes exactly one residue class of the variable r . The surviving values of r correspond to those odd integers $x = 2r + 1$ that are not divisible by the moduli already introduced in the sieve.

Finite verification principle

Let X be a prescribed upper bound and let

$$r_{\max} = \frac{X - 1}{2}.$$

A finite verification of the sieve up to X may be carried out by considering all integers

$$0 \leq r \leq r_{\max}$$

and by applying the exclusion rule

$$r \not\equiv \frac{d-1}{2} \pmod{d}$$

for the relevant odd moduli $d \geq 3$.

Equivalently, using the recursive system (M_t, S_t) defined above, the admissible indices are those satisfying

$$r \equiv s \pmod{M_t}, \quad s \in S_t.$$

For all integers $x = 2r + 1$ with $x < p_{t+1}^2$, this finite modular description gives the exact primes, since every composite integer below p_{t+1}^2 has at least one prime divisor among p_2, \dots, p_t .

Operational description without source code

The sieve may therefore be interpreted through the following mathematical operations.

1. Choose a finite bound X , and consider the corresponding interval $0 \leq r \leq (X - 1)/2$.

2. Introduce the odd prime moduli $p_2 = 3, p_3 = 5, p_4 = 7, \dots, p_t$ needed to cover the desired range.
3. For each modulus p_i , remove the single residue class

$$r \equiv \frac{p_i - 1}{2} \pmod{p_i}.$$

4. Retain the surviving values of r .
5. Translate each surviving value r back to the corresponding odd integer

$$x = 2r + 1.$$

6. Within the range $x < p_{t+1}^2$, the resulting values of x , apart from the exceptional value $x = 1$, are precisely the odd primes.

This procedure is a finite computational realization of the congruential criterion proved in the paper. It does not require any special programming language. Any numerical implementation is only an external realization of the same mathematical rule.

Table of the first forbidden classes

The first forbidden classes may be summarized as follows:

d	forbidden class for r	corresponding excluded $x = 2r + 1$
3	$r \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$	3, 9, 15, 21, ...
5	$r \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$	5, 15, 25, 35, ...
7	$r \equiv 3 \pmod{7}$	7, 21, 35, 49, ...
11	$r \equiv 5 \pmod{11}$	11, 33, 55, 77, ...
13	$r \equiv 6 \pmod{13}$	13, 39, 65, 91, ...

This table shows explicitly that ordinary divisibility of x is transformed into the exclusion of a single residue class for the inradius parameter r .

Elementary examples of the exclusion rule

The first exclusion rules are particularly transparent. For $d = 3$, the forbidden residue is

$$r \equiv 1 \pmod{3}.$$

Thus the excluded values

$$r = 1, 4, 7, 10, \dots$$

correspond to

$$x = 3, 9, 15, 21, \dots,$$

that is, to the odd multiples of 3.

For $d = 5$, the forbidden residue is

$$r \equiv 2 \pmod{5}.$$

Thus the excluded values

$$r = 2, 7, 12, 17, \dots$$

correspond to

$$x = 5, 15, 25, 35, \dots,$$

that is, to the odd multiples of 5.

For $d = 7$, the forbidden residue is

$$r \equiv 3 \pmod{7}.$$

Thus the excluded values

$$r = 3, 10, 17, 24, \dots$$

correspond to

$$x = 7, 21, 35, 49, \dots,$$

that is, to the odd multiples of 7.

More generally, for every odd modulus $d \geq 3$, the excluded values are

$$r = \frac{d-1}{2} + kd, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots,$$

and the corresponding odd integers are

$$x = 2r + 1 = d(2k + 1).$$

Hence the excluded values are exactly those for which $x = 2r + 1$ is divisible by d .

First modular levels

At the first level, using the modulus 3, one obtains

$$M_2 = 3, \quad S_2 = \{0, 2\}.$$

Indeed, the only residue removed modulo 3 is 1. The surviving residues give the odd integers not divisible by 3.

At the next level, introducing the modulus 5, one obtains

$$M_3 = 3 \cdot 5 = 15.$$

The residue classes surviving modulo 15 are

$$S_3 = \{0, 3, 5, 6, 8, 9, 11, 14\}.$$

These are precisely the residue classes of r for which $x = 2r + 1$ is not divisible by 3 or 5.

At the following level, introducing the modulus 7, the period becomes

$$M_4 = 3 \cdot 5 \cdot 7 = 105.$$

The set S_4 contains

$$|S_4| = \varphi(105) = 48$$

admissible residue classes. These classes repeat periodically modulo 105 and describe all odd integers $x = 2r + 1$ that are coprime to $3 \cdot 5 \cdot 7$.

This is exactly the wheel structure described in the main text. Each new prime modulus enlarges the period and removes one residue class inside each lifted family of residues.

Ordered generation

The construction is sieve-based, but it also has an ordered-generator interpretation. If

$$\mathcal{R} = \{r_1 < r_2 < r_3 < \dots\}$$

denotes the increasing sequence of surviving indices, then

$$p_k = 2r_k + 1$$

gives the increasing sequence of odd primes. Thus the ordering of the surviving values of r automatically induces the usual ordering of the corresponding prime numbers.

Remark on initialization. The first odd primes

$$3, 5, 7, 11$$

are naturally present at the beginning of the construction. They correspond to the first odd moduli used in the modular elimination process:

$$p_2 = 3, \quad p_3 = 5, \quad p_4 = 7, \quad p_5 = 11.$$

These cases are consistent with the theoretical formulation. Indeed, for $x < 13$ the primality condition is vacuously satisfied, because there are no odd divisors $d \geq 3$ with

$$d \leq \frac{x}{3}.$$

Consequently, the numbers 3, 5, 7, 11 naturally remain in the surviving set \mathcal{R} and appear as the first odd primes in the analytic formulation of the sieve.

A Zenodo reference record associated with the computational verification of this work is available at **10.5281/zenodo.21044931**. Moreover, the ordered structure of the sieve allows one to target the computation of a prescribed n -th prime without explicitly generating and storing the complete list of all preceding primes.

Thus, the appendix records only the mathematical meaning of the finite sieve.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated during the current study.

Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

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